

**Assessing the Influence of Information and Communication Technology Constraints on
Cassava Value Chain Actors in Anambra State**

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Abstract

Objective: The study examined the influence of information and communication technologies (ICT) constraints on cassava value chain actors in Anambra State. The specific objectives were to describe the socioeconomic characteristics of cassava value chain actors, identify the ICT used, and determine the major constraints on the use of ICT using multinomial regression analysis.

Methodology: The descriptive survey was used in the study. A multistage sampling technique was used to select 12 communities, giving a total of 319 respondents. Data were collected through the administration of a well-structured questionnaire and interview schedule. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics and multinomial logistic regression.

Results: The results indicated age of farmers between 21-40 is 42.9%; processors between 21-30 is 70.6%; marketers between 21-30 is 42.9% and consumers between 21-30 is 37% with majority (59.6%) of the farmers male; processors (66.7%) female; marketers 55.4%) female; also, majority of the farmers (60.2%): processors (61.1%); marketers (66.1%) and consumers (50.0%) were FSLC holders. Mobile phones, radio, television, computers, and the internet were the tools used in ICT. The multinomial logistic regression analysis of significant constraints on the use of ICT by cassava value chain actors showed erratic power supply, poor network coverage, lack of durable, inadequate ICT training centre, high cost of ICT facilities, high cost of internet subscription, high cost of maintenance and general lack of awareness of ICT are the significant constraints.

Conclusion: Potential interventions are needed to improve ICT access and usage among cassava value chain actors to improve their livelihood and reduce the cost of production for sustainable agriculture.

Keywords: Cassava, constraints, farmers, information and communication technologies, use

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become an integral part of modern-day businesses, revolutionising the way transactions are carried out and the speed at which information is disseminated. In the agricultural sector, ICT has the potential to significantly enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of value chains, including the cassava value chain (Corp, 2017). According to Oluwatosin (2019), cassava is an important staple crop for human consumption, and its value chain involves various actors such as farmers, processors, marketers and consumers. The use of information and communication technologies for development (ICT4D) has continued to evolve (Walsham, 2017), with increasing attention paid to their use for agricultural development in Africa (FAO, 2017). Farmers' increasing access to agricultural information in some parts of Africa has been linked to the evolution and uptake of digital technologies (Annan, 2016; Schwab, 2016). The increasing penetration of mobile networks, as well as the availability of mobile phones and their facilities, have created significant improvements in the ability to reach remote, dispersed, and under-served farmers irrespective of their environment and social status by facilitating access to extension services, agricultural information, and financial services (World Bank, 2018). Various agricultural information can be provided, including input data, best agricultural practices, transport, and market prices (World Bank, 2018). Agriculture is location-specific; therefore, farmers must get tailored advice on agricultural practices, input use, accurate local weather predictions, and real-time prices and

market information. It helps to create, acquire, store and disseminate agricultural knowledge for the rural communities (Ejemeyovwi et al., (2017). ICT has made a paramount contribution to modernising the traditional agricultural system, which is reflected

However, despite the numerous benefits that ICT can bring to the cassava value chain, some constraints hinder its full potential. These constraints may include limited access to ICT infrastructure, lack of technical skills among value chain actors, inadequate financial resources to invest in ICT tools, and resistance to change traditional practices. Understanding these constraints is crucial for developing strategies to overcome them and harness the full potential of ICT in the cassava value chain.

This research explores the influence of ICT constraints on cassava value chain actors and their implications for the overall efficiency and competitiveness of the value chain. By identifying and addressing these constraints, policymakers, researchers, and practitioners can work towards creating a more inclusive and sustainable cassava value chain that leverages the power of ICT to improve productivity, reduce post-harvest losses, enhance market access, and ultimately improve the livelihoods of smallholder farmers and other value chain actors.

Methodology

The study was carried out in Anambra State. Anambra is a state in the south-east geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The origin of the name is derived from the Anambra River (Omambala) which is a tributary of the River Niger. Its name is an anglicised version of the original 'Omombala' (Chukwuma et al., 2016). The capital and seat of government is Awka, while Onitsha, Nnewi and Ekwulobia are the biggest commercial and industrial cities. The state's theme is "Light of The Nation". Boundaries are formed with Delta State to the west, Imo State to the south, Enugu State to the east, and Kogi State to the north. The indigenous ethnic groups in Anambra State are the Igbo (98% of the population) and a small population of Igala (2% of the population) who live mainly in the north-western part of the state. It is made up of 21 Local Government Areas. It is located between latitude $5^{\circ} 32^1$ and $6^{\circ} 43^1$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 43^1$ and $7^{\circ} 22^1$ E of the area within the Greenwich meridian (Chukwuma et al., 2016). The area has a mean temperature of 30°C during the hottest (January) and 21°C during the coldest (July). The state has two distinct seasons, the dry and rainy seasons. The annual average rainfall is between 2000mm and 2300mm, distributed from March to November. The mean annual sunshine intensity is 5.2 hours, and the relative humidity is 28.2m^3 (Nigeria Meteorological Agency (NIMET), 2016). Anambra was created on 27 August 1991, and according to National Population Commission (NPC, 2006), the population was estimated to be 4,055,038 with a density of $846/\text{km}^2$ ($2,200/\text{sqm}$) and a total land mass of $4,854\text{km}^2$ (NPC, 2006). Agriculture is predominantly in rural areas.

A multistage sampling procedure was adopted. Anambra State was purposely selected because it is recognised as one of the significant cassava-producing states in Nigeria (Wossen, 2017). The three senatorial zones (Anambra North, Anambra Central and Anambra South) were selected in the first stage. In the second stage, two local government areas were randomly selected from each of the zones: in Anambra South Zone: -Orumba North and Orumba South Local Government Areas were selected; Anambra North Zone: Awka North and Awka South Local Government Areas; and Anambra Central Zone: Anambra East and Anambra West Local Government Areas. At stage three, a list of communities in each local government area was compiled, and a random selection of two communities from each of the six local government areas was made with the help of an agricultural extension agent. Also, with the help of contact farmers in the selected communities, 20 producers, 10 processors (small and medium processors), 10 marketers and 20 consumers were randomly selected based on the villages/clans in the communities. In the fourth stage, from the list, a random selection of 109 producers (farmers), 54 processors (medium and or large scale processors), 56 marketers and 100 consumers was performed across the selected communities. This gave rise to a sample size of 319 for the study. The data collected were analysed with the use of descriptive statistics and multinomial logistic regression.

Model Specification

The multinomial logistic regression equation is implicitly specified as follows:

$$\Pr(Y_i = j) = \frac{e^{B_{ixij}}}{1 + \sum_{m=1}^4 e^{B_{ixim}}} \quad J = 1, 2, 3, 4.$$

$$\Pr(Y = 0) = \frac{e^{B_{ixi0}}}{1 + e^{\sum e^{B_{ixij}}}}$$

This model can be transformed to:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \beta_8 X_8 + \text{et}$$

Where;

$\Pr(Y_i = j)$ = Probability of difference value chain actors

$\beta_0 - \beta_8$ = Vector of the estimated parameters.

j = Number of available enterprise options

m = level of the available enterprises (number)

X_i = Vector of the predictor (of the i th explanatory variable)

$Y_{i=1..4}$ = Cassava value chain actors output (i =farmers =1, marketers =2, processors =3 and consumers = 4)

- X₁ = Erratic power supply (dummy, Yes =1, No =0)
X₂ = Poor network coverage (dummy, Yes =1, No =0)
X₃ =Lack of durable ICT tools (dummy, Yes =1, No =0)
X₄ = Inadequate ICT training centre, (dummy, Yes =1, No =0)
X₅ = High cost of ICT facilities (₦)
X₆ = High cost of internet subscription (₦)
X₇ = High cost of maintenance (₦)
X₈ = General lack of awareness of the importance of ICT
Bo= intercept
 $\beta_1 - \beta_8$ = parameter estimate
e = error term

Results and Discussion

The results of the socioeconomic characteristics of the cassava value chain actors are presented in Table 1. Table 1 shows that a more significant proportion of the farmers (39.4%) were in the age bracket of 21-40, while the least (5.5%) were in the age fewer than 21 years. For the processors, the majority (70.6%) were in the age bracket of 21-30 while the least (3.7%) were those in age 50 and above. For marketers, more significant proportions (42.9%) were in the age bracket of 21-30, while the least (3.6%) were above 50 years. For the consumers, it shows that more significant proportions (37.0%) were in the age bracket of 21-30 while the least (6.0%) were under the age of less than 21. It implies that these actors (farmers, processors, marketers and consumers) are predominantly within the productive and economically viable age. This study is similar to Nuer (2018), who reported that youths are less conservative and more receptive to ICT, which entices them to engage in agribusiness and makes agriculture more attractive to them.

Sex: The majority (59.6%) of the farmers were males, while females accounted for 40.4%. For processors, the majority (66.7%) were females, while 33.3% of the respondents were males. For marketers, the majority (55.4%) were females, while 44.6% were males. For consumers, the majority (65.0%) were females, while 35.0% of the respondents were male. The results revealed that most females were marketers, consumers and processors, while the males were more farmers. This implies that males have higher access to productive resources such as land. This finding concurs with the result of Machina and Lubungu (2018), who reported that Male-headed households have higher access to productive resources and information, which increases the chances of using ICT in farming.

Marital status: Data in Table 1 shows that most (75.0%) of the farmers were married, while the least (1.9%) were widowed and divorced. For processors, the majority (72.2%) were

married, while the least (1.0%) were separated. Most marketers (67.9%) were married, while the least (1.8%) were separated and widowed. For consumers, the majority (73.0%) were married, but the least (1.0%) were separated. Economic imperatives of family responsibility may be the driving force behind married persons participating in the cassava value chain production; the mass unemployment may also account for unmarried persons going into cassava production in the face of a lack of paid employment worsened by the prevailing economic reforms such as fuel subsidy removal. This result is in line with the observation of Nwokoro (2017) that a larger percentage of married persons can be attributed to the highly patriarchal orientation in rural settings, which tends to give married individuals an edge over unmarried ones such that unmarried men and women are denied some entitlements to rural assets like land and livestock which constitute essentials of their livelihood.

Level of education: The results in Table 1 reveal that the majority (60.2%) of the farmers were first school living certificate (FSLC) holders while the least (4.6%) were those that had M.Sc/Ph.D. For the processors, the majority (61.1%) had FSLC, while the least (1.9%) had B.Sc/HND. For the marketers, the majority (66.1%) had first-school living certificate (FSLC) holders, whereas the least (1.8%) had OND/NCE. Most consumers (50.0%) had FLSC, but the least (4.0%) had M.Sc/PhD. This implies that the majority of the farming households have basic literacy but may not be said to be adequately educated. Education is a social capital which could positively impact a household's ability to make sound and informed production decisions. In addition, education is important to manage the farming business and the utilisation of ICT. This finding is similar to the finding of Igwe (2018), who reported that education and technical training positively affect farmers' use of ICT to boost their production and allow people to adapt more quickly to social and technical changes.

Household size: The results in Table 1 reveal that the majority (74.3%) of the farmers had household sizes of between 1-5 persons, while the least (11.9%) were those who had household sizes of 1-3. For processors, the majority (72.2%) had household sizes of 4-6, while the least (7.4%) were those that had a household size range of 7-10. For marketers, the majority (82.1%) had household sizes of 4-6, while the least (7.1%) had household size ranges of 7-10. For consumers, the majority (73.0%) had a household size range of 4-6, whereas the least (12.0%) had a household size of 1-3. This implies that many household members were not available in large numbers for cassava value chain activities. This is in line with Anate et al. (2018), who posited that the small household size could be a result of the yielding effect of awareness on family planning by rural dwellers and the benefits of family planning as a valuable tool in helping to space pregnancies, reducing the risks of maternal and child deaths through the use of ICT tools.

Table 2: ICT utilised by cassava value chain actors.

Variables (ICT Tools)	Farmers		Processors		Marketers		Consumers	
	Freq.	Percentage	Freq.	Percentage	Freq.	Percentage	Freq.	Percentage
Radio	10	9	7	13	10	18	8	8
Mobile Phone	75	69	24	44	35	63	77	77
Television	2	2	4	7	6	10	7	7
Computer	4	3	3	6	2	4	4	4
Internet	2	2	1	2	3	5	3	3
Audio Cassette	3	3	5	9	0	0	1	1
Camera	2	2	3	6	0	0	0	0
Video Recording	3	3	2	4	0	0	0	0
Remote sensing	8	7	5	9	0	0	0	0
Total	109	100	54	100	56	100	100	100

Field Survey, 2021

ICT Utilized By Cassava Value Chain Actors

Table 2 shows ICT used by cassava value chain actors (farmers, processors, marketers and consumers) in the study area. For the farmers, most (69%) of the respondents used mobile phones while the least (2%) used television, internet and camera. For the processors, a more significant percentage (44%) used mobile phones while the least (2%) used the Internet. For the marketers, the majority (63%) of the respondents used mobile phones, followed by those who used radio with 18%. For the consumers, the majority (77%) of the respondents used mobile phones, while the least (1%) used audio cassettes. Hence, ICT tools offer the opportunity to reach often remote, dispersed and poorly serviced farmers and other actors by overcoming distance barriers and poor road infrastructure. This finding is consistent with Baumüller (2018), who stated that radio and television are among the most widely used media for disseminating information to rural audiences across Africa, together with mobile phones, due to the increased ownership and widespread use among farmers.

Table 3: Major constraints of ICT faced by cassava value chain actors using multinomial regression analysis

Variables	Farmers		Processors		Marketers		Consumers	
	Coefficient	P[Z >]						
Erratic power supply(X1)	-1.814	0.006	-1.297	0.086	-1.277	0.005	-1.315	0.005
Poor network coverage (X2)	-1.008	0.005	-1.112	0.005	-1.094	0.005	-0.152	1.581
Lack of durable ICT tool (X3)	-1.188	0.004	-1.181	0.005	-1.185	0.005	-0.133	0.382

Inadequate ICT training centre (X4)	- 1.011	0.006	-1.049	0.005	-1.029	0.005	-1.051	0.006
High cost of ICT facilities (X5)	-1.010	0.006	-1.084	0.006	-1.022	0.006	-1.025	0.006
High cost of internet subscription (X6)	--1.028	0.004	-1.069	0.005	-1.038	0.005	-1.059	0.004
High cost of maintenance (X7)	-1.050	0.006	-1.184	0.006	-1.053	0.005	-1.115	0.006
Lack of awareness of ICT(X8)	-1.004	0.003	-1.047	0.005	-1.173	0.004	-1.123	0.004
Multinomial logistic regression								
Number of observations		319						
LR Chi		214.24						
Prob>Chi		0.001						
McFadden		0.57						
Cox and Snell		0.49						
Nagelkerke		0.51						
*** p=0.01, ** p=0.05 and * p=0.10								
Source: Field survey, 2021								

The multinomial logistic regression model was fitted, and the summary is presented in Table 3. The diagnostic results, which described the relationship between the dependent and independent variables, were also presented. It can be observed that the chi-square statistic value is 215.99 with a corresponding probability of p-value < 0.05.

This confirms the adequacy of the model and implies that at least most of the coefficients of the explanatory variables were significant. The strength of the model was also tested using McFadden. The McFadden value was 0.57, which is 57%. This implies that the independent variables in the model explained 57% of variations in the dependent variables. Cox and Snell, and Nagelkerke R squares, on the other hand, indicate that 49% and 51% of the variations in the model were explained by the explanatory variables fitted. The result was analysed based on different cassava value chain actors.

Erratic power supply

Results in Table 3 show that coefficients of erratic power supply (X₁) as one of the major constraints to the use of ICT were negative and significant at 5% level of significance for farmers' group (-1.814); processors' group(-1.297); marketers' group (-1.277) and consumers' group (-1.315). This implies that an increase in the major constraints of ICT faced by actors (farmers' group, processors' group, marketers' group, and consumers' group) led to a likely decrease in the use of ICT. This finding is in line with the result of Demenongu (2018), who stated that Nigeria was constrained by a poor electricity supply, resulting in many farmers abandoning the use of ICT.

Poor network coverage and lack of durable ICT tools

The coefficients of poor network coverage (X_2) and lack of durable ICT tools (X_3) as major constraints of ICT were negative and significant at a 5% level for the farmers' group (-1.008; -1.188); processors' group (-1.112; -1.181) and marketers' group (-1.094; -1.185). However, coefficients of poor network coverage and lack of durable ICT tools (X_2) were negative and insignificant at the 5% level for the consumers' group (-0.152; 0.382). It implies that an increase in these significant constraints (poor network coverage and lack of durable ICT tools) of ICT by actors (farmers' group, processors' group and marketers' group) can result in the likelihood of a decrease in the use of ICT by the farmers, processors and marketers. This finding aligns with the results of Shankar et al. (2020), who stated that due to the limited access to ICT networks due to poor networks and durable ICT tools, most people in rural areas do not prioritise information, communication and technology.

The results in Table 3 show that the coefficient of inadequate ICT training centre (X_4); high cost of ICT facilities (X_5); high cost of internet subscription (X_6); high cost of maintenance (X_7) and lack of awareness of ICT (X_8) were negative and significant at 5% significant level for farmers' group (-1.011, -1.010, -1.028, -1.050 and -1.004); processors' group (-1.049, -1.084, -1.069, -1.184 and -1.047); marketers' group (-1.029, -1.022, 1.038, -1.053 and -1.173) and consumers' group (-1.051, -1.025, -1.059, -1.115 and -1.123) respectively. It implies that an increase in these significant constraints (inadequate ICT training centre, high cost of ICT facilities, high cost of internet subscription, high cost of maintenance and general lack of awareness) of ICT by the actors (farmers' group, processors' group, marketers' group and consumers' group) led to likelihood decrease in the use of ICT by cassava value chain actors (farmers, processors, marketers and consumers). This finding is in line with the report of Titilope (2017), who identified the high cost of ICT facilities, inadequate ICT training centres, high cost of internet subscription, and high cost of maintenance and general lack of awareness, poor infrastructure and meagre income as significant constraints to use of ICT by farmers in Sub Saharan African.

Finally, the major constraints (erratic power supply, poor network coverage, lack of durable, inadequate ICT training centre, high cost of ICT facilities, high cost of internet subscription, high cost of maintenance and lack of awareness of ICT) of ICT faced by cassava value chain actors were significant and negative and decreased use of ICT in the study area.

Conclusion

Using multinomial logistics analysis, the study evaluated the influence of information and communication technology (ICT) constraints on cassava value chain actors in Anambra State. The constraints (erratic power supply, poor network coverage, lack of durable, inadequate ICT training centre, high cost of ICT facilities, high cost of internet subscription, high cost of maintenance and general lack of awareness of ICT) to use of ICT by cassava value chain actors

had significant and adverse effects on cassava value chain actors in the study area. The usage of ICT tools such as mobile phones, radio, television, and video cameras, among others, is very important to agricultural production as relevant agricultural information can be disseminated to farmers, processors, marketers and consumers.

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